

Application of a New Non-relativistic Self-consistent-Field Method to Heavy Closed-Shell Atoms

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A simple density functional quadratic equation has been numerically and self-consistently solved for calculating the radial densities, energies and several other expectation values for the ground states of three noble gas atoms, with the nuclear charge $Z=54, 86$ and 118 . In almost all the cases, the present results agree with other calculated values to within a few per cent.

DURING the last fifteen years, considerable effort has been devoted by several research groups in order to obtain a *single* equation for the direct calculation of the electron density in many-electron systems^{1–10}. Such efforts bypass the many-particle wavefunction and the Schrödinger equation too, if possible, thereby generating the promise of great reduction in *ab initio* computational labour and of gaining transparent physical insights into diverse atomic, molecular and solid state (including surfaces) phenomena. Although a great deal of progress has been achieved in this area, a completely satisfactory *ab initio* single density equation is yet to be obtained¹¹.

In this paper, we apply a simple non-relativistic density functional method, recently developed by us, to the calculation of electronic structure and properties of the ground states of three heavy closed-shell (noble gas) atoms, of nuclear charge $Z=54, 86$ and 118 respectively. We compute the radial densities, various energies and several expectation values of these atoms in order to test the short-range (close to the nucleus) and long-range (further away from the nucleus) accuracy of the calculated densities. As will be seen below, our very simple method satisfactorily reproduces most of these quantities.

The new self-consistent-field density functional method:

The key equation in density functional theory (DFT)^{12–17} is the Euler-Lagrange equation (ELE),

$$\frac{\delta E[\rho]}{\delta \rho} = \mu \quad (1)$$

where, $\rho(\vec{r})$ is the electron density, μ is a Lagrange multiplier (chemical potential) and the energy functional $E[\rho]$ is given by

$$E[\rho] = \int v(\vec{r}) \rho(\vec{r}) d(\vec{r}) + \frac{1}{2} \iint \frac{\rho(\vec{r}) \rho(\vec{r}')}{|\vec{r}-\vec{r}'|} d\vec{r} d\vec{r}' + T[\rho] + E_{xc}[\rho] \quad (2)$$

where $v(\vec{r})$ is the external (electron-nuclear attraction) potential, $T[\rho]$ the kinetic energy (KE) functional and $E_{xc}[\rho]$ the exchange-correlation energy (XCE) functional. Exact analytical forms for $T[\rho]$ and $E_{xc}[\rho]$ are not known.

There have been many attempts¹⁸ to approximate the KE and XCE functionals. In this paper, we will employ the following KE functional¹⁹ which appears to be the best practical compromise as far as its local and global characteristics as well as the behaviour of its functional derivative are concerned,

$$T[\rho] = C_k \int \rho^{4/3} d\vec{r} - \frac{1}{40} \int \frac{\vec{r} \cdot \nabla \rho}{r^2} d\vec{r} \quad (3)$$

$$C_k = (3/10)(3\pi^2)^{2/3}$$

The functional in equation (3) has been found to be quite good in both structure⁸ and dynamics⁴ calculations. As the XCE functional, we take the following,

$$E_{xc}[\rho] = E_x[\rho] + E_c[\rho]$$

$$= -C_x \int \rho^{4/3} d\vec{r} - \int \frac{\rho}{(9.81 + 21.437 \rho^{-1/3})} d\vec{r} \quad (4)$$

$$C_x = (3/4\pi)(3\pi^2)^{1/3}$$

The first term in equation (4) is the Dirac exchange functional while the second term is a Wigner-type parametrised correlation functional²⁰ which reproduces well²¹ atomic correlation energies with near-Hartree-Fock densities²².

Using equations (2)–(4), the ELE (1) can be written as a simple quadratic equation,

$$a\theta^2 + b\theta + c = 0 \quad (5)$$

where, $\theta = \rho^{1/3}$; $a = -(5/3) C_k r$; $b = (4/3) C_x r$;

$$c = -(1/40)(1/r) + Z - r \int \frac{\rho(\vec{r}')}{|\vec{r}-\vec{r}'|} d\vec{r}' + \mu r + r \left[\frac{9.81 + 28.583 \rho^{-1/3}}{(9.81 + 21.437 \rho^{-1/3})^2} \right]$$

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Equation (5) has been solved numerically and self-consistently for closed-shell atoms with $Z=54$, 86 and 118. A square mesh has been chosen to discretise r as $r_j=x_j^2$; $x_j=x_{j-1}+h$, and θ as θ_j , $j=1, \dots, M$. One begins with an initial guess for μ and ρ for constructing c in equation (5). With this c , equation (5) is solved by changing μ through a Newton-Raphson technique such that the normalisation

$$\int \rho \, dr = N; N \equiv \text{the number of electrons}$$

is preserved ('inner iteration'). After fixing μ , c is reconstructed by using a density which is a weighted combination of the old and the current values of ρ such that convergence is assured. Then, equation (5) is solved again ('outer iteration') and with the same c the 'inner iteration' is continued. The whole process is continued in single precision until both ρ and μ become self-consistent. The method is very simple and has been described in detail elsewhere³ without including electron correlation. An input profile, $y=r \rho^{1/2}=19r \exp(-7r)$ was employed.

Results and Discussion

Table 1 presents the numerical results while Fig. 1 depicts the radial density for the three atoms. Since the present calculations are essentially of a modified Thomas-Fermi-Dirac-Weizsaecker-type, the radial density plots represent an 'average' picture in which density oscillations characteristic of atomic shell structure do not appear. A similar plot was obtained for the Ar atom in the TFD- λ W framework²⁵. In order to test the quality of the calculated density, expectation values such as $\langle r \rangle$, $\langle r^2 \rangle$, $\langle 1/r \rangle$ and $\langle 1/r^2 \rangle$ have been computed and compared with approximate Hartree-Fock (HF) calculations^{22,24}, wherever available.

As seen from Table 1, the virial theorem ($-V/T=2.0$) is well satisfied by the present calculations. The various energy values agree with the HF values to within 3 per cent and the trend in

energy values is also reproduced well. Comparing the $\langle r \rangle$, $\langle r^2 \rangle$ and $\langle 1/r \rangle$ values for the Rn atom with triple-zeta Roothaan-Hartree-Fock calculations²⁴, we find that the agreement between the two sets of values is quite good, considering the great simplicity of the present calculations. However, the $\langle 1/r^2 \rangle$ value is considerably overestimated because the present calculations place greater electron density near the nucleus, compared with the HF density. Similar conclusions are likely to be valid for the other two atoms as well. The small negative values of the chemical potential μ are as expected. Interpreting μ as $(\delta E/\delta N)^{26}$, the present calculations indicate that it is easier to add an electron to the 118-atom than to either Rn or Xe.

An additional comparison of energy values can be made on the basis of Z -expansion of the non-relativistic energies of neutral atoms²¹, viz.

$$-E(Z) = C_7 Z^{7/2} + C_6 Z^2 + C_5 Z^{5/2} + C_4 Z^{4/2} + C_3 Z + Z[9.81 + 21.437 (Z^2/V_0)^{-1/2}]^{-1} \quad (6)$$

In equation (6), the last three terms have been added by Chattaraj *et al.*²¹ while the previous three terms have been derived by other workers. The universal constants in equation (6) have the following values (a.u.): $V_0=7.218207$, $C_3=0.00126492$, $C_4=0.0129783$, $C_5=0.2699$, $C_6=-0.5$, $C_7=0.76874512$. We therefore obtain, $E(54)=-7230.134$, $E(86)=-21862.917$ and $E(118)=-46323.832$, which compare nicely with the total energy values in Table 1. It may be noted that an estimated relativistic total energy for the 118-atom is -54712.41 a.u.²⁶. Our non-relativistic calculations on the 118-atom thus appear to be the first reported for this atom. According to Chattaraj *et al.*²¹, the relativistic contribution to the total energy of the 118-atom is -7371.181 a.u. which, when added to the non-relativistic energy in Table 1, gives -54251.0 a.u. as the total energy.

Conclusion :

In contrast to other methodologies in quantum chemistry, the present method employs neither

TABLE 1—CALCULATED ELECTRONIC PROPERTIES (a.u.) FOR THREE NOBLE GAS ATOMS IN THEIR GROUND STATES WITH NUCLEAR CHARGE $Z=54, 86$ AND 118

Properties*	Z	54(Xe)		86(Rn)		118
		This work	Ref. 22	This work	Ref. 24	This work
T		7 461.5	7 232.047	22 291.8	21 866.775	47 310.7
T_{TF}		6 846.9	—	20 788.5	—	44 175.2
$-V$		14 849.3	14 464.177	44 623.1	43 733.532	94 190.6
$-V/T$		1.990	2.000	2.002	2.000	1.991
$-E$		7 987.8	7 232.130	22 331.3	21 866.757	46 879.8
$-\mu$		0.1	—	0.15	—	0.2
$\langle r \rangle$		38.2	—	54.1	53.648	68.3
$\langle r^2 \rangle$		63.6	—	85.4	81.210	103.9
$\langle 1/r \rangle$		325.5	—	613.7	604.392	943.5
$\langle 1/r^2 \rangle$		22 066.8	—	57 010.3	39 026.902	106 995.0

* T ≡kinetic energy; T_{TF} ≡Thomas-Fermi kinetic energy computed with the calculated density; V ≡potential energy, E ≡total energy; μ ≡chemical potential.

Fig. 1. Plot of radial density ($4\pi r^2 \rho$) against \sqrt{r} , in a.u. for three noble gas atoms in their ground states, with the nuclear charge Z being (a) 54, (b) 86 and (c) 118. The radial density peak is (a) 79.64 at $\sqrt{r}=0.31$, (b) 147.18 at $\sqrt{r}=0.29$ and (c) 223.73 at $\sqrt{r}=0.27$.

a differential nor an integro-differential equation. The quadratic equation employed here is very easy to solve for the ground state of any atom with hardly any increase in computational labour from a light to a heavy atom. The results agree with much more elaborate and laborious computations to within a few per cent while the trends are reproduced quite satisfactorily, except those quantities which magnify the errors in the computed density near the nucleus. With further refinements, the present approach has the potential to develop into a powerful method for understanding structures and dynamics of atoms, molecules and solids.

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